

Combining ability and heterosis for some physiological traits in rice

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We crossed modern rice genotypes IR8, IR36, IR42, IR46, IR68, and IR21015-80-3-3-1-2 (OM86) from IRRI, and OM80 and OM201 from Vietnam in a half-diallel set. The plot was laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications during the 1991 wet season. Single seedlings of parents and F_2 s were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing and received 80-40-0 kg NPK/ha. In eight selected crosses we assessed heterosis and heterobeltiosis for yield, leaf area index (LAI), net assimilation rate (NAR), crop growth rate (CGR), leaf area duration (LAD), high density grain index (HDI), and harvest index (HI).

HDI was calculated as the number of high density grains (more than 1.20 specific gravity) divided by spikelets/panicle.

High significant mean squares of all traits for both general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability

(SCA) indicated the importance of both additive and nonadditive gene action. However, the SCA^2 were higher than the GCA variances (GCA^2), suggesting the prevalence of nonadditive gene effects for CGR, NAR, HDI, HI, and grain yield (Table 1).

The general predictability factor for LAI was high (above 0.70) at maximum tillering and ripening, indicating that additive gene action was more important

than nonadditive gene action for this trait.

The predictability factors were less than 0.50 for the remaining characters, thus showing the equal importance of both types of gene actions in the inheritance of these traits.

OM80 appeared to be the best combiner for yield; IR46, OM80, IR68, and OM86 for LAI at heading, IR36 for NAR (panicle initiation to heading); OM201 for NAR (heading to harvest);

Table 1. Components of variance and predictability factor.^a

Character	σ^2 GCA	σ^2 SCA	Predictability factor
Yield	52.1	129.6	0.44
LAI			
Maximum tillering	0.09	0.02	0.91
Heading	20.8	52.2	0.44
Ripening	21.9	10.1	0.81
NAR			
Maximum tillering to heading	34.4	75.5	0.22
Heading to ripening	0.99	2.20	0.47
CGR			
Maximum tillering to heading	1.27	3.59	0.41
Heading to ripening	10.5	46.6	0.31
LAD			
Maximum tillering to heading	549.0	1413.0	0.43
Heading to ripening	924.0	2126.0	0.46
HDI	763.0	1923.0	0.44
Panicles/hill	12.0	27.9	0.46
Filled grains/panicle	1381.1	3050.3	0.47
100-grain weight	107.2	267.3	0.44
HI	0.05	0.11	0.44

^aPredictability factor $2 \sigma^2$ GCA / (2 σ^2 GCA + σ^2 SCA)

Table 2. Percent heterosis (H) and heterobeltiosis (HB) for selected crosses.^a

Cross	Yield	LAI (heading)	NAR		CGR		LAD		HDI	HI	
			1	2	1	2	1	2			
IR36/OM80	(H)	60.5**	76.5**	-8.6	49.2**	-22.6	116.7**	63.6**	67.3**	3.7 ns	-14.8
	(HB)	43.7**	53.0**	-13.0	46.1**	-41.1	93.4**	39.6**	45.5**	-1.8	-23.3
IR36/IR68	(H)	63.6**	17.3*	34.9**	19.2*	-37.2	-16.6	9.6*	6.5*	2.0 ns	5.0*
	(HB)	62.0**	-11.2	21.7**	-18.8	-49.9	-48.9	-15.4	-18.6	-4.5	-11.7
IR36/IR46	(H)	60.9**	48.0**	-22.2	-29.4	-19.1	-30.2	45.5**	41.8**	9.4*	-9.9
	(HB)	57.3**	32.9**	-34.0	-52.1	-32.2	-52.6	32.3**	31.2**	6.9*	-16.7
IR8/IR46	(H)	60.4**	31.7**	-21.6	-37.8	-5.1	2.6 ns	31.8**	34.1**	11.9*	-3.0
	(HB)	62.5**	31.2**	-36.8	-53.8	-24.2	-22.5	31.5**	32.7**	6.2*	-3.9
IR8/OM201	(H)	46.7**	-16.9	35.7**	-27.5	66.7**	1.6 ns	-15.4	-4.7	11.4*	38.3**
	(HB)	37.5**	-30.2	9.4*	-45.9	27.7**	-23.9	-29.6	-16.3	4.8*	30.0**
OM80/IR42	(H)	30.3**	-20.8	29.2**	-0.9	12.8*	-13.7	-23.0	-21.1	3.2 ns	13.4*
	(HB)	21.1**	-31.6	19.8**	-7.1	-16.1	-16.1	-27.5	-26.3	-0.2	12.2*
OM80/OM201	(H)	23.0**	-2.8	31.9**	8.0*	26.6**	13.4*	-6.1	-3.6	-8.6	15.2*
	(HB)	6.8*	-15.9	17.0**	-27.3	18.3**	-18.1	-17.0	-10.8	-10.7	10.4*
IR46/IR42	(H)	51.9**	27.0**	-18.3	-69.1	-26.5	-63.6	23.9**	22.1**	4.4*	12.0*
	(HB)	49.1**	9.4*	-22.2	-78.5	-40.1	-73.0	9.2*	7.3*	4.3*	9.8*

^a1 = maximum tillering to heading, 2 = heading to ripening. * and ** = significant at the level of 0.05 and 0.01, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

IR8, IR36, and IR46 for CGR (panicle initiation to heading); and IR36, IR42, and OM201 for HI.

Heterosis and heterobeltiosis for these traits in the selected crosses are presented in Table 2. Heterosis over midparents for

yield ranged from 23 to 63.6%; heterosis over better parents ranged from 6.8 to 62.5%. Most of the F_1 means of HDI deviated slightly from parental and mid-parental values in all crosses, indicating the absence of heterosis for the trait.

HI obtained high positive values in the divergent genotype cross of IR8/OM201. We also observed heterosis in the desirable direction in LAI, NAR, and CGR, from heading to ripening, in some crosses. ■

Breeding methods

Ability of some cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines of rice to produce hybrid seed

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We evaluated the ability of some CMS lines to establish satisfactory seed set with restorer (R) lines. A crossing block with 10 CMS and 5 restorer lines was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications during 1990 wet season. A line $\times$ tester model of crossing was used to make 50 crosses.

In both replications, each A line was flanked by a R line on both sides (1:2 ratio of A to R lines). Three staggered plantings of R lines at 5-d intervals were made to produce the continuous pollen supply that would ensure synchronized flowering of A and R lines. For each row, 15 plants for both A and R lines were maintained at 20- $\times$ 20-cm spacing.

We grew a row of Purple Puttu between crosses to intercept pollen.

We allowed the plants to outcross naturally. We aided pollination by tapping the R lines with bamboo sticks and passing ropes across the lines during anthesis. The hybrid seeds were collected at maturity from A lines. We used the mean seed set of 15 plants in each A line for the analysis.

The analysis of variance for seed set in a randomized block showed significant differences among the 50 crosses (see table). TNMS37 A/ARC11353 R recorded the maximum seed set (24.8%), followed by V20 A/IR54 R (24.4%). The line TNMS37 A crossed well with all R lines except IR36 R (2.25%); it had a mean seed set of 12.3%. When the mean seed set percentages of the R lines—in combination with all the A lines—were compared, IR46 R had the highest mean seed set of 12.3%, followed by IR54 R with 12%.

Because R lines combine differently with different male sterile lines, it is recommended that the parents be selected on the basis of seed set in

individual crosses rather than on their overall performance. In this context, the hybrids TNMS37 A/ARC11353 R, V20 A/IR54 R, and IR54756 A/IR54 R are the best combinations to produce increased hybrid seed. ■

Genetic analysis of yield components in rice involving CMS lines

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Success in breeding for quantitative traits depends upon the gene action involved for the traits concerned and the nature of the gene effects controlling the character.

We conducted a study to deduce the nature of gene action governing the traits that are economically important in rice. We used a line $\times$ tester method of mating. Ten cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines (IR54753, IR54756, V20, ZS97, Intan mutant, Pushpa, Mangala, Improved Sona, TNMS37, and ADCMS-1) were used as the lines. Five restorer lines (IR36, IR46, IR54, IR9761-19-1, and ARC11353) served as the testers.

Seed set in A/R crosses by natural outcrossing.

Male sterile line	Seed set (%)					Mean
	ARC11353 R	IR36 R	IR9761-19-1 R	IR46 R	IR54 R	
IR54753 A	13.40	5.60	2.19	17.70	7.84	9.35
Intan Mutant A	4.83	5.70	5.02	4.60	5.40	5.11
Z.S. 97 A	9.80	12.99	10.74	15.51	8.60	11.53
Pushpa A	13.40	5.29	4.30	6.90	12.90	8.56
Mangala A	6.40	2.26	0.39	12.14	6.00	5.44
IR54756 A	6.09	14.70	2.44	11.70	21.14	11.21
Improved Sona A	16.09	6.60	7.35	18.40	9.06	11.50
TNMS37 A	24.75	2.25	13.46	14.97	11.21	13.33
ADCMS-1-A	9.09	10.95	14.00	18.15	13.45	13.13
V20 A	12.25	15.45	3.90	2.40	24.36	11.67
Mean	11.61	8.18	6.38	12.25	12.00	-
SE (d) = 1.44						
LSD = 2.89						

Ratio of GCA and SCA variances.

Character	GCA variance (σ^2A)	SCA variance (σ^2D)	Ratio of $\sigma^2A:\sigma^2D$
Days to 50% flowering	7.03	11.43	0.62
Plant height	0.29	27.26	0.01
Productive tillers	0.09	1.56	0.06
Boot leaf area	1.77	16.26	0.11
Panicle exertion	0.48	1.30	0.37
Panicle length	0.05	1.76	0.03
Grains per panicle	92.90	186.34	0.50
100-grain weight	0.001	0.02	0.05
Grain yield	2.98	5.75	0.51